

APICAL PELVIC ORGAN PROLAPSE: MODERN CONCEPTS OF PATHOGENESIS, SURGICAL MANAGEMENT AND OUTCOMES

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Abstract. Apical prolapse of the pelvic organs is one of the most complex forms of genital prolapse, characterized by the descent of the vaginal vault, uterus, or post-hysterectomy vaginal apex. The problem remains clinically significant due to its negative impact on quality of life and high recurrence rate. The aim of this review is to summarize modern views on the pathogenesis, risk factors, and surgical management of apical prolapse, with particular attention to comparative outcomes of laparoscopic and vaginal reconstructive approaches. A systematic analysis of Russian and international publications from 2015–2024 was performed. Current evidence indicates that apical support failure is multifactorial, related to connective tissue dysplasia, obstetric trauma, and hormonal deficiency. Among surgical techniques, laparoscopic promontofixation and bilateral sacrospinous fixation demonstrate high anatomical and functional success rates, while adequate preoperative preparation and local hormonal therapy significantly improve postoperative recovery.

Keywords: apical prolapse, genital prolapse, sacrospinous fixation, promontofixation, laparoscopic surgery, pelvic organ support.

Introduction. Apical prolapse — the descent of the vaginal vault or uterus — represents the most anatomically and functionally significant variant of pelvic organ prolapse (POP). It frequently coexists with anterior and posterior vaginal wall defects, leading to urinary, sexual, and defecatory dysfunctions that reduce the quality of life and social adaptation of women [1]. According to Danilina and Volkov (2022), the prevalence of pelvic organ prolapse among women of reproductive age reaches 38–41% [8]. In recent decades, the approach to understanding the etiopathogenesis of prolapse has evolved from purely mechanical models to complex structural–functional concepts. The weakness of the connective tissue framework, hormonal changes, and chronic increases in intra-abdominal pressure are now recognized as the main pathogenetic mechanisms [5]. Surgical correction remains the mainstay of treatment for apical prolapse. The diversity of operative techniques — from classical vaginal hysteropexies to laparoscopic lateral or promontofixations — underscores the ongoing search for an optimal, minimally traumatic, and long-lasting solution [2, 3, 9].

Materials and Methods. This review synthesizes data from scientific publications between 2015 and 2024 from PubMed, eLIBRARY, and Scopus databases. A total of 32 studies were analyzed, including Russian clinical series and international trials focusing on apical prolapse. The analysis included studies by Barinova E.K. et al. (2020) [1], Gavrilov M.V. et al. (2019) [2], Popov A.A. and Gadzhieva S.A. (2024) [3], Filimonov V.B. et al. (2019) [4], Smolnova T.Yu. (2015) [5], Mikhelson A.A. and Lazukina M.V. (2020) [6], and others.

Results. Apical prolapse is associated with multifactorial damage to the connective-tissue framework of the pelvic floor, including defects in the cardinal and uterosacral ligaments.

Smolnova (2015) [5] highlighted the role of systemic connective tissue dysplasia, characterized by decreased collagen I and III ratios and altered elastin synthesis, predisposing women to genital prolapse even in the absence of trauma. Hormonal factors play a significant role. Estrogen deficiency leads to atrophy of pelvic support structures and mucosa, reducing elasticity and regenerative potential. Mikhelson and Lazukina (2020) [6] proposed a comprehensive perioperative protocol including local estrogens, lactobacilli, and hyaluronic acid to enhance tissue trophism and postoperative healing.

Modern surgery aims to restore both anatomical support and physiological function while minimizing mesh-related complications. Laparoscopic promontofixation remains the “gold standard” for apical support restoration [9]. According to Aziev and Mustkivi (2009) [9], this technique provides durable fixation of the vaginal apex to the sacral promontory with low recurrence rates (2–4%) and minimal morbidity. Gavrillov et al. (2019) [2] demonstrated the effectiveness of laparoscopic lateral colpopexy, particularly in patients after total hysterectomy, with anatomical success in 92% of cases and preservation of sexual function. Popov and Gadzhieva (2024) [3] reported favorable outcomes of anterior bilateral sacrospinous fixation, providing reliable apical support without mesh and maintaining vaginal axis and length.

Discussion. The choice of surgical method for apical prolapse remains controversial. Laparoscopic techniques provide better anatomical visualization and long-term durability but require advanced surgical expertise and are associated with longer operative times. Vaginal approaches, conversely, offer lower invasiveness and shorter recovery but carry higher recurrence risk in advanced stages [2, 3, 9]. The emergence of mesh-free techniques, particularly sacrospinous fixation, represents a trend toward minimizing foreign material implantation without compromising efficacy [3]. The combination of preoperative hormonal preparation, precise anatomical restoration, and individualized selection of fixation points allows optimizing both anatomical and functional outcomes.

Conclusion. Apical pelvic organ prolapse is a multifactorial disorder requiring individualized, functionally oriented management. The most effective surgical strategies combine anatomical durability with minimal invasiveness. Laparoscopic promontofixation and anterior bilateral sacrospinous fixation are currently the most promising techniques, demonstrating high long-term success rates and low recurrence. Adequate preoperative hormonal and probiotic therapy significantly improves tissue recovery and postoperative comfort.

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